

INDIVIDUAL PREVENTION IN THE ACTIVITIES OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

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Over the years of independence, comprehensive measures have been implemented in the republic to prevent offenses and combat crime, which has allowed us to achieve positive results in ensuring law and order and significantly improving the criminal situation in the country.

In order to create an effective system of coordination of activities for the prevention of offenses and the fight against crime, the introduction of modern organizational and legal mechanisms for the prevention and suppression of violations of laws, fundamental reforms in the field of crime prevention have been carried out in the country since 2017.

According to statistics, the total number of registered crimes in 2019 in the republic is 46.09 thousand cases, and in 2020 this number increased by 34.6% and amounted to 62.08 thousand crimes. In 2022, 105.2 thousand crimes were committed [3].

At the same time, the number of offenses such as robbery and robbery is growing especially rapidly (by 152%), theft (by 142%), fraud (by 134%), hooliganism (by 93%). All these crimes are committed against the property and peace of citizens [7].

The above statistics state that prevention inspectors are faced with the tasks of early prevention and identification of offenses, the causes of offenses and conditions that facilitate them to take legal measures against offenders. To solve this task, the inspector of crime prevention must take measures to prevent individual offenses.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 14, 2014 "On the prevention of offenses" defines the main measures of individual prevention of offenses. Individual prevention of offenses may include the following measures: preventive conversation, official warning, informing about the causes of offenses and conditions that contribute to them, social rehabilitation and social adaptation, preventive accounting, referral to compulsory treatment and administrative supervision.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 2, 2021 No. PP-5050 "On additional organizational measures to further improve the activities of internal affairs bodies in the field of public safety and combating crime" for early prevention of offenses among

minors based on the principle of “Safe educational institution” was introduced into the structures of district and city bodies the position of “inspector-psychologist on juvenile issues” [7].

The main tasks of psychological inspectors are to improve the psychological environment in secondary educational institutions by working with each student, forming an irreconcilable attitude to offenses among minors, targeted work with problem students directly in their places of residence with the involvement of parents. Work with this category of persons in the prevention of offenses is bearing fruit.

In order to improve the effectiveness of the work of prevention inspectors, an electronic system for placing persons on preventive registration has been introduced since July 1, 2021. Preventive accounting is one of the measures of individual prevention of offenses, which is a set of preventive measures carried out by the internal affairs bodies in relation to certain categories of persons, in order to correct them and prevent the commission of a repeat offense [7].

Article 35 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Prevention of Offenses” lists persons in respect of whom preventive records are kept. In respect of previously convicted persons, after they have served a criminal sentence, with the exception of persons in respect of whom administrative supervision has been established; in respect of whom a guilty verdict of the court has entered into force without imposing punishment; in respect of whom the criminal case was terminated without resolving the issue of guilt in accordance with article 84 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan or a decision was made to refuse to initiate criminal proceedings on non-rehabilitating grounds; accused of committing a crime, in respect of whom a preventive measure was chosen that was not related to detention; committed administrative offenses provided for by articles The Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Administrative Responsibility; returned from specialized educational institutions [5].

Based on the data of the Republican Interdepartmental Commission for the Prevention of Offenses and the Fight against Crime for 12 months of 2020, preventive accounting was established for 182,774 persons, This indicator for 2023 is over 639 thousand persons [1].

The prevention inspector, when carrying out preventive measures with persons for whom preventive accounting has been established, must take into account individual characteristics, age, gender, mental state, social status, education, interests and abilities.

In addition, the prevention inspector, for the targeted implementation of individual preventive measures in relation to persons on the preventive register, taking into account the public danger of each person, the type of offense committed by him, based on the objects of public threat, conducts preventive work on his administrative territory, as well as reporting on the results of these preventive measures.

Separately, it should be noted that the post of inspector of crime prevention among women has been introduced into the system of crime prevention. To date, as a result of the work carried out, there has been a sharp decrease in the number of crimes committed by women. The proportion of female offenders was 12.0% of the total number of detected crimes [3].

In conclusion, it should be noted that the prevention inspector, conducting individual prevention of offenses, implements measures aimed at providing legal, social, psychological, medical, pedagogical and other assistance to victims of offenses, persons with antisocial behavior, prone to committing offenses, who have committed offenses, as well as instilling in them socially accepted norms and rules of behavior.

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